

Preparation and Infrared Spectra of Some Dibenzyl-Sulphoxide Complexes of Organotin Halides

T. N. SRIVASTAVA, P. C. SRIVASTAVA and KUSUM SRIVASTAVA

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 25 October 1975; accepted 11 February 1976

About a dozen hexa co-ordinated complexes of organotin halides with dibenzyl sulphoxide have been isolated and characterised. The spectral changes in the infrared spectrum of the ligand on complexation are briefly described. Metal associated absorption such as Sn-R, Sn-X and Sn-O have been identified in the far infrared region and the stereochemistry of the complexes on the basis of the data is proposed.

THE synthesis and the structure of the molecular adducts of organotin (IV) halides with dialkyl- and diaryl sulphoxides have attracted attention of several workers¹⁻¹⁵ in recent years. Thus Langer and Blut¹ isolated adducts of organotin halides with dimethylsulphoxide and examined their infrared spectra. Tanaka² recorded the infrared spectra of the complexes $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2DMSO$ ($R = CH_3, C_2H_5$; $X = Cl, Br$) and on the basis of metal associated absorptions concluded that in the octahedral geometry, the two chlorine atoms occupy *cis* position and the two R groups are *trans* to each other. Kitching *et al.*^{3,4} obtained several complexes of methyltin halides with dibenzyl, dimethyl, diethyl, and methyl-benzyl sulphoxides in the crystalline state and determined their structures with the help of vibrational and proton magnetic resonance data. Randall *et al.*⁵ synthesised 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 adducts of diphenyltin dichloride with some sulphoxide donors and examined their Mössbauer and infrared spectra. Liengme *et al.*⁶ prepared a number of complexes of diphenyl and dimethyltin halides with oxygen donor molecules including sulphoxides and collected Mössbauer, infrared and Raman spectral evidence in favour of the proposed structure. X-ray spectroscopy has also been successfully applied to determine structure of $Me_2SnCl_2 \cdot 2DMSO$ ^{7,8}. In their recent communications, Srivastava and Saxena^{9,10} reported several complexes of diaryltin dihalides ($R = o$ -tolyl, m -tolyl or p -tolyl; $X = Cl, Br$ or I) with dimethyl- and diphenyl sulphoxides and examined their infrared and ultra violet spectra. Srivastava and Agarwal¹¹ have also reported IR studies of complexes of dimethyl sulphoxide with diaryltin dinitrates and diisothiocyanates¹¹.

Excepting a brief report by Kitching *et al.*⁴ on the adduct of dibenzyl sulphoxide with diphenyltin dichloride, there seems to be no systematic study of dibenzylsulphoxide complexes of organotin halides. In this communication, we report about a dozen new 1 : 2 complexes of dibenzyl sulphoxide with organotin halides ($R =$ butyl (Bu), phenyl (Ph), p -tolyl (pt)

or benzyl (Bz); $X = Cl$ or Br). Their infrared spectra have been reported and an attempt has been made to suggest their geometry on the basis of metal-ligand absorptions.

Experimental

The molecular adducts described in this investigation are obtained by the direct interaction of the Lewis acids and bases in appropriate solvents using conventional ground glass apparatus. Manipulations were carried out in a dry box flushed with nitrogen.

The conductance measurements of representative complexes were made by Phillips, magic eye, conductivity bridge model PR-9500 and the molecular weights were determined cryscopically using Beckmann thermometer of accuracy 0.01°. The infrared spectra in nujol were recorded in the range 4000-250 cm^{-1} using Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer. A few samples were also screened upto 100 cm^{-1} using Hitachi spectrophotometer at the Otto Maass Chemical Laboratories, McGill University, Montreal Canada.

Materials

The organotin halides namely butyltin trichloride, -tribromide, phenyltin trichloride, dibutyltin dichloride, -dibromide diphenyltin dichloride, and tribenzyltin chloride were obtained from Alpha Inorganics and used without further purification. Diphenyltin dichloride, -dibromide, *p*-tolyltin dichloride, -di-bromide and triphenyltin chloride were prepared by the reported methods¹⁶. Dibenzyl sulphoxide (E. Merck) was used after recrystallisation from ethanol.

Preparation of the complexes

In a typical experiment to a solution of 5 mmole of organotin halide in 10 ml. of a suitable solvent was added 12 mmole of dibenzyl sulphoxide in 20 ml. of the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for several hrs after which the excess solvent was distilled off. The desired complex was then precipitated by

the addition of petroleum ether. The crude product was recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride, washed with diethyl ether and dried in vacuum. Experimental results are listed in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data summarised in Table 1 indicate that complexes of molar ratio 1 : 2 (Lewis acid : base) are invariably formed. A change in the ratio in which the reactants are mixed, does not produce an effect on the composition of the product.

All complexes are white crystalline solid soluble in common organic solvents such as acetone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene. They are thermally stable and are not significantly affected

by atmospheric oxygen and moisture. The molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solution in nitrobenzene is observed in the range 1.0 to 5.4 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ indicating absence of ionic species. However, experimentally determined molecular weight in freezing nitrobenzene is considerably lower than the formula weight suggesting significant dissociation of the complexes in solution.

Infrared spectra

The infrared active absorptions of diagnostic value are listed in Table 2. Above 600 cm⁻¹ only two absorptions of structural significance namely S = O and C-S stretchings have been discussed whereas below 600 cm⁻¹ an attempt has been made to identify all important fundamental modes of vibration.

TABLE 1. EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR R_nSnX_{4-n} .2DBSO

R _n SnX _{4-n}	Solvent*	m.p. °C	Calculated %			Found %		
			C	H	Sn	C	H	Sn
1. BuSnCl ₃	A	111—117	51.72	4.98	16.03	51.20	4.91	16.01
2. BuSnBr ₂	A	120—122	43.83	4.22	13.58	43.75	4.10	13.33
3. PhSnCl ₃	B	74—76	53.50	4.33	15.61	53.54	4.29	16.00
4. Bu ₂ SnCl ₂	B	101—103	56.54	6.02	15.58	56.83	5.96	15.92
5. Bu ₂ SnBr ₂	B	94—97	50.64	5.39	13.95	50.17	5.31	13.70
6. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂	C	131 (125—26)*	59.70	4.72	14.80	59.62	4.62	14.73
7. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂	C	129	53.75	4.25	13.30	53.60	4.28	13.45
8. <i>pt</i> ₂ SnCl ₂	C	152	60.57	5.05	14.30	60.45	5.02	13.95
9. <i>pt</i> ₂ SnBr ₂	C	174	54.72	4.56	12.92	54.40	4.49	12.90
10. Bz ₂ SnCl ₂	C	108	60.57	5.05	14.30	60.52	4.98	14.42
11. Ph ₂ SnCl	B	91—92	65.32	5.09	14.08	65.10	4.94	14.20
12. Bz ₂ SnCl**	B	92—95	66.25	5.52	13.41	—	—	11.58

* A = methylene dichloride, B = chloroform, C = acetone.
** slightly hygroscopic.

TABLE 2. INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF R_nSnX_{4-n} .2DBSO.

Assignment	DBSO	1*	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
$\nu(S=O)$	1037vs	940vs	950vs	945vs,br	970vs	970vs	949vs	950vs	945s	945s	990s	975vs
$-\Delta\nu(S=O)$		97	87	92	67	67	88	87	92	92	47	62
$\nu(C-S)$	681m	695vs	690s	692vs	698s	695s	690sh	690m	698s	697s	695vs	700s
$\nu(Sn-O)$		425s	428s,br	430w	395s	400s	410m	420w	421w	418m	405w	405w
		370w	375w	380vw	340m	380s	367w	369w	370vs	365s	363w	370m
$\delta_{as}(C-S-O)$	366s	330m	330s	330s	320m	330m	326w	328m	328m	332s	330w	322m
$\delta_s(C-S-O)$	328s	305s	305s	315w	295s	310w	304m	302s	304s	300vs	308w	290sh
$\delta_{as}(C-S-O)-\delta_{as}(C-S-O)$	38	25	25	15	25	20	22	26	24	32	22	32
$\nu_{as}(Sn-R)$		570m	560m	270m	560m	562m	290s	275s	272vs	272vs	290s	277w
$\nu_s(Sn-R)$		—	515w	238m	515w	520m	236vs	236s	240m	242vs	—	—
$\nu_{as}(Sn-X)$				255s			258s	148m	244m	142m		
$\nu_s(Sn-X)$				204m			204m	—	206m	—		
in plane ring bending (u)				220s			219s	222s	218s	212s		
out of plane ring bending (x)				194s			200s	198s	202s	201w		
				185s			190s	178s	180s	180s		

m = medium, s = strong, w = weak, v = very, sh = shoulder, br = broad,
* Number refers to compounds in Table 1.

Ligand absorptions

In the infrared spectra of free dibenzyl sulphoxide an absorption of strong intensity at 1037 cm^{-1} is considered predominantly due to $\text{S}=\text{O}$ stretching mode of vibration¹⁷. On co-ordination from the oxygen atom, it is invariably shifted to lower frequency region due to decrease in π bonding. In the present investigation the negative shift of the $\text{S}=\text{O}$ stretching frequency in all the complexes ranges from 47 to 97 cm^{-1} and in almost all the complexes, the absorption band on co-ordination splits into two bands due to lowering of symmetry, and indicating strong possibility of the two ligand molecules occupying *cis* position in the octahedral geometry. Several workers^{19,20} have co-related the magnitude of $-\Delta\nu(\text{S}=\text{O})$ with the donor acceptor interaction strength. From a perusal of the results presented in Table 2, the following order for the relative acceptor strength of Lewis acids employed is apparent.

(where R = butyl, phenyl).

In case of diorganotin dihalides a variation of R group shows the order *p*-tolyl > phenyl > butyl > benzyl.

The asymmetric and symmetric C-S stretching in unco-ordinated base lie at 681 cm^{-1} respectively. The former mode of vibration is found to undergo a positive shift in the spectra of all the complexes and occurs at $695 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$, while the latter could not be identified due to its weak intensity and masking by other absorptions in the same region. The results definitely suggest absence of co-ordination from sulphur atom of the Lewis base².

Weber¹⁸ has examined the spectra of certain dibenzyl sulphoxide complexes of transition metals and has assigned absorptions around 480 and 350 cm^{-1} to $\delta(\text{C-S-O})$ on the basis of the reported study of Green²¹. However, Tanaka² identified this absorption in the DMSO complexes of the tetrahalides around 335 and $306 \pm 8\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Oertel²² in a study of DMSO complexes of antimony and bismuth halides also assigned absorptions associated with this mode of vibrations in the same vicinity. The assignments of Green²¹ and Weber¹⁸ are undoubtedly incorrect since the absorptions around 480 cm^{-1} is definitely associated with the mode 'y', (Whiffen's nomenclature)²³, an out of plane ring deformation, and occurs in all aryl derivatives. In this investigation, the $\delta(\text{C-S-O})$ has therefore, been identified at 366 and 328 cm^{-1} in the free base which undergoes a negative shift on complexation due to co-ordination from the oxygen atom of the ligand and weakening of the C-S-O band. The observed separation between the symmetric and asymmetric modes in the unco-ordinated base $\delta_s(\text{C-S-O}) - \delta_{as}(\text{C-S-O})$ is 38 cm^{-1} while in the complexes it ranges between 15 to 32 cm^{-1} . The decrease in separation is an indication of complexation as suggested by Oertel²².

Metal absorptions

The Sn-O stretching absorption in sulphoxide complexes of organotin halides has been identified by various workers^{2,5,6} in the vicinity of 400 cm^{-1} , excepting in $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{DPSO}$ and $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{DPSO}$ where it is found to occur at a lower frequency around 268 cm^{-1} . In the complexes, reported in this communication, two absorptions at 412 ± 18 and $360 \pm 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ identified in the spectra of all the complexes but absent in that of the free base, are assigned to this mode of vibration which strongly supports our suggestions of bonding through the oxygen atom of the ligand. The relative position of Sn-O stretching vibration is roughly related to $\Delta\nu(\text{S}=\text{O})$. A larger negative shift in $\nu(\text{S}=\text{O})$ is accompanied by a shift in the positions of $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ towards higher frequency side, suggesting stronger co-ordination.

In complexes of butyltin halides, two absorptions at 565 ± 5 and $518 \pm 3\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to Sn-C stretchings. The corresponding absorptions in aryltin halides appear at 280 ± 10 and $239 \pm 3\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and have been named as Sn-aryl stretchings though in fact they are aromatic ring vibrations *t* and *t'* (Whiffen's nomenclature)²³ highly sensitive to the mass of the metal atom. As suggested earlier, the position of the absorptions in the parent Lewis acids and their complexes remains unaltered²⁴⁻²⁶.

The Sn-Cl stretching mode of vibration has been identified in diphenyltin dichloride at 364 and 356 cm^{-1} . The corresponding bands in the bipyridyl complex occur at 253 and 245 cm^{-1} showing a negative shift of about 100 cm^{-1} attributed to the increase in co-ordination number of the metal atom^{25,26}. The absorptions in the same vicinity have also been identified by Tanaka² while examining the spectra of complexes of organotin halides with dimethyl sulphoxide. Randall *et al.*^{5,6} have made assignments in this region without taking into account $\delta(\text{C-S-O})$ and aromatic ring bending modes "u" and "x" which lie in the same region²⁷. The absorptions assigned to Sn-Cl stretching vibrations in the range $319-336\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are undoubtedly due to $\delta(\text{C-S-O})$, while those assigned in the vicinity of 200 cm^{-1} may be due to aromatic ring vibration "a". It is difficult to make unambiguous assignments in this region of the spectrum due to its complexity and poor resolution. We could screen a few samples in the far infrared region and by a critical comparison of the spectrum of the free ligand with those of the complexes, have made assignments listed in Table 2 which confirm that the Sn-X absorptions are shifted to lower frequency from the positions in the parent Lewis acids on increase in co-ordination number of the metal atom.

The analytical data coupled with conductance and molecular weight results indicate formation of neutral hexa-co-ordinated molecular adducts. The infrared unequivocally suggests co-ordination through the oxygen atom of the ligand and that the two molecules of the base occupy *cis* position in the octahedron. As regards the position of the two R groups and the two chlorines, the spectral data indicate two Sn-R and two Sn-Cl stretching modes,

a situation similar to that met by Liengme *et al.*⁶ in similar sulphoxide complexes. It is, therefore, suggested that the two chlorine atoms may occupy *cis* position and that the two R groups are *trans* to each other, the appearance of the two Sn-R absorptions being due to distortion of the octahedron and C-Sn-C angle being not 180°. The conclusion is based on the observations of the above mentioned workers⁶ who have supported their conclusion through Mossbauer spectroscopic data.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow for affording laboratory facilities and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (PCS). We are also indebted to Canadian International Development Agency and National Research Council of Canada for the award of a research associateship to one of us (TNS), which enabled us to collect the spectral data and obtain organotin halides.

References

1. H. G. LANGER and A. H. BLUT, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 288.
2. T. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.* 1967, 1, 217.
3. W. KITCHING, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 3689.
4. W. KITCHING, C. J. MOORE and D. DODDRELL, *Austral J. Chem.* 1969, 22, 1149.
5. R. S. RANDALL, R. W. J. WEDD and J. R. SAMS, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1971, 30, C-19.
6. B. V. LIENGME, R. S. RANDALL and J. R. SAMS, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1972, 50, 3212.
7. N. W. ISSACS, and C. H. L. KENNARD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, A 1257.
8. N. ISSACS, C. H. L. KENNARD and W. KITCHING, *Chem. Comm.*, 1968, 820.
9. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and K. L. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1971, 48, 449.
10. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and K. L. SAXENA, *Indian J. Chem.* 1973, 11, 294.
11. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and M. P. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem.* 1970, 8, 652, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 3416.
12. J. GOPALKRISHNAN and C. C. PATEL, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1968, 27, 475.
13. B. C. CLARK and R. G. GOEL, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1967, 7, 263.
14. V. B. RAMOS and R. S. TOBIAS, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1974, 30A, 181.
15. F. A. COTTON, R. D. BARNES and E. BANNISTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 2199.
16. R. K. INGHAM, S. D. ROSENBERG and H. GILMAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, 59, 459.
17. R. S. DRAGO and D. W. MEEK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 1446.
18. J. H. WEBER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 2813.
19. T. TANAKA and T. KAMITANI, *Inorg. Chem. Acta.*, 1968, 2, 175.
20. R. W. J. WEDD and J. R. SAMS, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1970, 48, 71.
21. J. H. S. GREEN, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1968, 24A, 1627.
22. R. P. OERTEL, *Spectrochim Acta.* 1970, 26A, 659.
23. D. H. WHIFFEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1350.
24. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 98.
25. R. C. POLLER, J. N. R. RUDDICK, M. THEVARASA and W. R. McWHINNIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 2327.
26. J. R. MAY, W. R. McWHINNIE and R. C. POLLER, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1971, 27A, 969.
27. I. WHARF, J. Z. LOBOS and M. ONYSZCHUK, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1970, 48, 2787.